

Case Report -3

Comprehensive Insights into Pancreatic Cystic Neoplasms: A Case Series on Diagnosis, Surgery, and Histopathology

Jincy Elsam John¹, Royce An Abraham¹, Deepak K Johnson², Sujith Philip³

¹ Pharm D interns, ^{2,3} Senior Consultants & HOD

¹ Nazareth College of Pharmacy, Othara, Thiruvalla, Kerala,

²Department of Medical Gastroenterology & Hepatology, ³ Department of Gastrointestinal Surgery: Believers Regional Institute of Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Transplantation (BRIGHT), Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Thiruvalla, Kerala

Keywords: Pancreatic cystic neoplasms, Mucinous cystic neoplasms, Pancreatectomy, Computed Tomography

Corresponding Author: jincy123john1@gmail.com

Abstract

Pancreatic cystic neoplasms (PCNs) are rare tumors with malignant potential therefore requiring accurate diagnosis. This case series analyzes seven PCN cases at Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Kerala, India, emphasizing diagnostic challenges, surgical management, and outcomes. Mucinous cystic neoplasms (MCNs) were the most common type, primarily affecting middle-aged women. Surgical treatment was guided by standard criteria for symptomatic or high-risk lesions. Post-operative histopathology confirmed diagnoses and highlighted the need for multidisciplinary care. Early detection and tailored management are essential to prevent malignancy and improve patient outcomes.

Introduction

Pancreatic cystic lesions or neoplasms (PCLs/PCNs) are a diverse group of tumors, accounting for about 1% of pancreatic tumors and 1- 15% of primary pancreatic cystic masses. Most often, they are detected incidentally during imaging for nonspecific symptoms like abdominal

pain or diarrhea.(1) Advances in cross-sectional imaging and increased awareness have led to a rise in diagnosis, especially in older adults. PCNs are classified into neoplastic and non -neoplastic types, with true neoplastic cysts representing 15-20 % and they include intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasms (IPMN), mucinous cystic neoplasms, solid pseudopapillary neoplasms, and cystic pancreatic neuroendocrine tumors, while nonneoplastic types encompass serous cystadenomas, simple cysts and lymphoepithelial cysts. They can be benign or malignant and accurate diagnosis is crucial, as management varies significantly between both types.(2) Surgical resection, while necessary for some, is not always ideal due to potential complications, making surveillance a safer alternative in select cases. Advanced modalities like endoscopic ultrasound have enhanced diagnostic accuracy, improving treatment decision-making and definitive diagnosis often requires histopathological analysis of resected material due to challenges in distinguishing types through imaging alone.(2, 3)

Here, in this study, we discuss 7 cases of PCNs focusing on their diagnostic characteristics, surgical management and oncological outcomes.

Samples

Seven patients who underwent surgery for PCNs at Believers Church Medical College Hospital, Kerala, India, recently were included in this study.

Standard guidelines were used as indications for surgery. This included symptoms related to pancreatic pathology, tumor markers and imaging findings. Demographic data, biochemical

parameters, imaging findings, surgical details were recorded.

Results

Six females and one male patient with ages ranging from 30-75 underwent surgery for PCN. Almost all the patients had non-specific abdominal pain.

The demographic details, signs and symptoms, diagnosis and type of surgery of the patients are presented in Table 1. Four out of seven patients had mucinous cystic neoplasm and subtotal or distal pancreatectomy with splenectomy was the preferred surgical intervention.

Table 1: Demographic details, signs and symptoms, diagnosis and type of surgery

Sl. No.	Age	Gender	Signs And Symptoms	Diagnosis	Cea Value	Surgery
1	30	F	Right upper limb, Chest, hypochondriac pain weight loss	Solid pseudopapillary epithelial neoplasm (SPEN)	--	Distal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
2	70	M	Radiating abdominal pain	Intra ductal mucinous neoplasm (IPMN)	158.12 ng/ml	Subtotal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
3	74	F	Vomiting, loose stools	Mucinous cystadenoma pancreas (MCN)	---	Open subtotal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
4	48	F	Abdominal pain and distension vomiting	Mucinous cystic neoplasm of pancreas	147.22 ng/ml	Subtotal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
5		F	Right sided abdominal pain -8-9 months	Mucinous cystic neoplasm of pancreas	2.99 ng/ml	Subtotal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
6	39	F	Abdominal distension	Mucinous cystic neoplasm of pancreas	---	Subtotal pancreatectomy Splenectomy
7	40	F	Left sided abdominal pain-` 3 weeks	Serous cystadenoma	---	Distal pancreatectomy Splenectomy

The Computed Tomography (CT) images of the seven patients highlighting the findings are shown in Figures 1a-1g.

Solid pseudopapillary epithelial neoplasm (SPEN)

Fig.1a

Intraductal Papillary Mucinous Neoplasm

Fig.1b

Mucinous cystadenoma pancreas

Fig.1c

Large Mucinous cystic neoplasm

Fig.1c

Mucinous cystic neoplasm

Fig.1e

Mucinous cystic neoplasm with necrosis

Fig.1f

Macrocystic serous cystadenoma pancreas

Fig.1g

Fig.1a represents the CT image of solid pseudopapillary epithelial neoplasm, *Fig.1b* represents intra ductal mucinous neoplasm, *Fig.1c* is mucinous cystadenoma pancreas, *Fig.1d, 1e, 1f* shows mucinous cystic neoplasm of pancreas and *Fig.1g* shows serous cystadenoma

Discussion

The study highlights the clinical diversity and surgical management outcomes of pancreatic cystic neoplasms in a tertiary care setting. Among the seven cases analyzed, the predominance of mucinous

cystic neoplasms in middle-aged women is consistent with global epidemiological trends, reinforcing the gender predilection and age distribution of PCNs.(4, 5) MCNs are rare mucin-producing tumors that mainly occurs in the pancreatic body or tail

and are distinguished by ovarian-type stroma.(6) The nonspecific nature of symptoms such as abdominal pain underscores the diagnostic challenges, often necessitating advanced imaging and tumor marker evaluation for accurate identification.(7) Surgical intervention, primarily distal or subtotal pancreatectomy with splenectomy, was the definitive treatment, aligning with established guidelines for symptomatic and high-risk lesions.(8) Post-operative histopathological confirmation remains crucial, as imaging alone is often insufficient for precise diagnosis.(9) These findings emphasize the importance of a multidisciplinary approach in the management of PCNs, combining vigilant surveillance, timely surgical intervention, and histological analysis to optimize patient outcomes while minimizing unnecessary surgeries.(10)

Conclusion

Cystic neoplasms of the pancreas represent a rare but significant subset of pancreatic lesions with diverse histological and clinical presentations. In this series of seven cases, surgical management proved to be a safe and effective approach for both diagnostic confirmation and therapeutic resolution. The spectrum of cystic neoplasms observed in our series highlights the critical importance of comprehensive preoperative evaluation, including imaging and cytological assessment, to guide clinical decision-making. While mucinous cystic neoplasms and serous cystadenomas constituted the majority of cases, the presence of rare entities underlines the need for heightened clinical suspicion and multidisciplinary collaboration. Histopathological

examination remains the cornerstone for definitive diagnosis, underscoring the need for surgical intervention in suspected cases, even when clinical and radiological findings are inconclusive.

Our findings emphasize the role of early and accurate identification of pancreatic cystic neoplasms to prevent progression to malignancy, improve patient outcomes, and expand the understanding of these enigmatic lesions. Further studies with larger cohorts are essential to refine diagnostic algorithms and optimize treatment strategies for these patients.

Abbreviations

Pancreatic cystic neoplasms (PCNs), Mucinous cystic neoplasms (MCNs), intraductal papillary mucinous neoplasms (IPMN), Computed Tomography (CT)

References

1. Kılıç MÖ, Erdoğan A, Ceylan C, Saylam B, Tez M. PANCREATIC CYSTIC NEOPLASMS: A CASE SERIES. *International Journal of Surgery and Medicine*. 2016;2(4):197-. Available from: <https://www.bibliomed.org/fulltextpdf.php?mno=215275>
2. Hutchins GF, Draganov PV. Cystic neoplasms of the pancreas: a diagnostic challenge. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2009;15(1):48-54.
3. Patel N, Asafo-Agyei KO, Osueni A, Mukherjee S. Pancreatic cysts. 2018. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK525979/>
4. Crippa S, Salvia R, Warshaw AL, Domínguez I, Bassi C, Falconi M, et al. Mucinous cystic neoplasm of the pancreas is not an aggressive entity: lessons from 163 resected patients. *Ann Surg*. 2008;247(4):571-9.
5. Menon G, Hoilat GJ, Babiker HM, Mukkamalla SKR. Mucinous cystic

- pancreatic neoplasms. StatPearls [Internet]: StatPearls Publishing; 2023. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK448105/>
6. Nilsson LN, Keane MG, Shamali A, Bocos JM, van Zanten MM, Antila A, et al. Nature and management of pancreatic mucinous cystic neoplasm (MCN): a systematic review of the literature. *Pancreatology*. 2016;16(6):1028-36.
 7. Şolea SF, Brisc MC, Orăşeanu A, Venter FC, Brisc CM, Şolea RM, et al. Revolutionizing the Pancreatic Tumor Diagnosis: Emerging Trends in Imaging Technologies: A Systematic Review. *Medicina*. 2024;60(5):695.
 8. D'Haese JG, Werner J. Surgery of cystic tumors of the pancreas-why, when, and how. *Visceral Medicine*. 2018;34(3):205-9.
 9. Koo CS, Ho KY. The role of EUS-FNA in the evaluation of pancreatic cystic lesions. *LWW*; 2020. p. 71-5.
 10. Law JK, Hruban RH, Lennon AM. Management of pancreatic cysts: a multidisciplinary approach. *Current opinion in gastroenterology*. 2013;29(5):509-16.
-